

SURVEY AND ASSESSMENT OF WATER RESOURCES STATUS OF COUNTRY MAIN CANAL

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the analysis of the resources of the Karshi main canal, irrigation systems, the current state of irrigated lands and the existing hydrotechnical facilities in the canal.

Introduction. The main task of the Karshi main canal is to provide water for irrigation of the Karshi desert lands. Under the project, 402,000 hectares of land (392,000 hectares in Uzbekistan and 10,000 hectares in Turkmenistan) will be irrigated without dams from Amudarya. The opposite trunk channel consists of two parts: the first part is the main part, and the second part is the working part. The main part of the Karshi main canal is located in the territory of Lebap region of the state of Turkmenistan, starting from Pulizinda headland, it goes north and flows into the low plain of Talimarjan (Fig. 1). The length of the main part is 77.6 km from the Amudarya to the working part of the canal, and its normal water transfer capacity is 175 m³ per second and the maximum capacity is designed to transfer 195 m³ per second.

Figure 1. Location scheme of anti-main channel facilities.

Research materials and their analysis. From the Amudarya to the I-pumping station, the canal flowed through an earthen bed. The length of the main water supply channel to the I-pumping station is 20.45 km.

From the 1st pumping station to the 7th pumping station, the channel is trapezoidal and covered with concrete covers. The design parameters of the aggregates of the part of the channel from the 1st pumping station to the 6th pumping station in the territory of Turkmenistan are presented in Table 1.

From pumping station 1 to pumping station 2 20.7 km, from pumping station 2 to pumping station 3 1.38 km, from pumping station 3 to pumping station 4 20.0 km, from pumping station 4 to pumping station 5 4.72 km and from the 5th pumping station to the 6th pumping station is 8.4 km.

Table 1.

Design parameters of each pumping station and its aggregates

Name of pumping stations	Started in the year	Number of units, units	Model of pump units	Electrod vi gate power, kW	Water discharge capacity of 1 pump unit m3/sec
1 - HC	1973	3	ОПВ 11-260	12500	36
		3 (1,3,4 ar)	300BO-37/26ц		39
2 - HC	1973	6	ОПВ 10-260	12500	36
3 - HC	1973	6	ОПВ 10-260	12500	36
4 - HC	1973	6	ОПВ 10-260	12500	36
5 - HC	1974	6	ОПВ 10-260	12500	36
6 - HC	1974	6	ОПВ 10-260	12500	36

-the pumping station is located at PK 204+37 of the canal and the 2nd pumping station is located at PK 411+19 of the canal. The total length of the channel is 20.7 km. The width of the bottom of the channel is 7.07 m, the bank slopes are 2.5 m, the maximum width of the channel is 40.27 m, the slope is 0.00015. The canal has PK 217+30 1 water measuring hydropost, PK 265 road bridge, PK 298 and PK 302 aqueduct, PK 307 railway crossing, PK 310 dukers.

- 2nd pumping station is located at PK 411+19 of the canal and the 3rd pumping station is located at PK 424+95 of the canal. The total length of the channel is 1.38 km. The width of the bottom of the channel is 7.07 m, the bank slopes are 2.5 m, the maximum width of the channel is 40.27 m, the slope is 0.00015.

-3rd pumping station is located at PK 424+95 of the canal and the 4th pumping station is located at PK 624+95 of the canal. The total length of the channel is 20.0 km. The width of the bottom of the channel is 7.07 m, the bank slopes are 2.5 m, the maximum width of the channel is 40.24 m, and the slope is 0.00015. There is a road bridge at PK 589+41 of the channel.

- 4th pumping station is located at PK 624+95 of the canal and the 5th pumping station is located at PK 672+23 of the canal. The total length of the channel is 4.72 km. The width of the bottom of the channel is 7.07 m, the bank slopes are 2.5 m, the maximum width of the channel is 40.27 m, the slope is 0.00015. PK 647 and PK652 of the canal have a water measuring hydropost, PK650 has a main structure for water intake to the Mirishkor canal (water intake capacity 105 m³/s).

-5th pumping station is located at PK 672+23 of the canal and the 6th pumping station is located at PK 756+23 of the canal. The total length of the channel is 8.4 km. The width of the bottom of the channel is 7.07 m, the bank slopes are 2.5 m, the maximum width of the channel is 40.27 m, the slope is 0.00015.

The counter-machine channel cascade belongs to the class of large hydrotechnical structures and is a complex irrigation system operationally dependent on water flow parameters and pump station operation mode. The operating mode of each pumping station in the cascade of the counter-machine channel is continuously dependent on the operating mode of other pumping stations in the cascade and the dynamics of the water level and consumption in the channel. That is, for the operation of 5 aggregates in the I-pumping station, the water level in the channel bringing water to the I-pumping station is at 244.08 points relative to BKT (Baltic coordinate system), for the operation of 5 aggregates in the II-pumping station, the water in the channel bringing water to the III-pumping station level is 258.2 marks, the water level in the channel bringing water to the III-pump station for the operation of 5 aggregates in the III-pumping station is 282.07 marks, for the operation of 5 aggregates in the IV-pumping station, the water level in the water supply channel to the IV-pumping station is at 303.46 marks, for the operation of the 5 aggregates in the V-

pumping station, the water level in the water supply channel to the V-pumping station is at 327.27 marks, and finally, the VI-pump for the operation of 5 aggregates at the station, the water level in the channel supplying water to the VI-pumping station is required to be at 350.27 marks. Therefore, the working mode of the pumping stations in the cascade of the Karshi machine channel is continuously dependent on the water level in the channel, consumption and the working mode of the pumping stations in each cascade.

The anti-machine channel cascade was put into operation in 1973, and during the past period, the pumping station, its aggregates and the system of pressure pipes were reconstructed several times. In addition, most of the working parts of large pumping units are repaired in the repair shops operating in the system of the Canal Use Department.

Conclusion. Due to climate change and anthropogenic influences, the water level and flow in the Amudarya River change dramatically throughout the year. These situations, in turn, require the assessment of the operating mode of the pumping stations in the cascade of the Anti-machine channel and the calculation of their hydraulic parameters.

At the same time, scientific and technical issues related to the assessment of the operation mode of pumping stations in large cascade machine channels depending on the hydraulic parameters of the water flow in the channel and the calculation of hydraulic-energetic parameters have not been sufficiently studied..

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